

An LMI Approach to the Control of a Class of Nonlinear Systems ¹

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Abstract

The paper considers the control of the class of nonlinear systems that can be represented by the convex hull of a collection of local linear approximates. Usage of such quasi-linear modeling reduces the problem of the robust stabilization of the class with static state or dynamic output feedback, against modeling error and parametric uncertainty, to a Linear Matrix Inequality (LMI) problem.

1. Introduction

For more than a decade, a family of mathematical models, developed via independent approaches, has used linear combinations of basis functions to match the I/O behavior of a system within specified accuracy. The polynomial model of [1] has been proposed as a universal approximator of complex dynamics. Nonlinear ARMAX models, also known as NARMAX, have been introduced for the same purpose [2,3]. Parallel to the above research, the development of fuzzy models has provided another I/O based method that approximates static nonlinearities, intrinsic to industrial processes and control actions of skilled operators [4]. This method, often called Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy modeling, quickly expanded to include dynamic system modeling [5-7]. Theoretical justification of fuzzy models as universal approximators has been given by [8]. Unlike NARMAX, fuzzy models have been analyzed mostly from their state space representations [9,10]. Methodologies that treat the identification problem of both I/O and state space fuzzy models have been proposed [11,12]. Finally, it has been shown that fuzzy and NARMAX models are equivalent [13,14].

The main objective of nonconventional modeling is to

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provide for model based control of complex nonlinear plants. For fuzzy or NARMAX modeling, usage of the obtained model for control design purposes was demonstrated respectively by [15] and [16]. More recently, fuzzy or NARMAX model based control has succeeded to exploit further the particular structure of these models [17-19,9]. This quasi-linear structure, i.e., the fuzzy model being a nonlinear superposition of linear local models, has prompted efficient analysis techniques established mainly on the concept of quadratic stability [15,20,10]. Using quadratic criteria as well as other stability tools, which originate also from the mainstream control literature, several design issues have been addressed, such as observer-based feedback [21,22] and H_∞ control design [23,24].

Analysis and design of fuzzy models via a common Lyapunov function—the pivotal point of quadratic stability—offers an additional advantage. The majority of control problems associated with fuzzy models and the plants these represent, can be formulated as convex optimization programs with LMI constraints [25]. Such formulation, often called the LMI approach, has provided fertile ground for development of the related theory and design since its advent as a fuzzy model control tool [26]. The synergy between the quasi-linear structure of fuzzy models and the ability of the LMI approach to solve (if feasible) a variety of control problems defined on such structure, has been very fruitful [27,28].

The primary objective of this paper is to provide a systematic and efficient approach for control of any complex nonlinear plant that can be approximated by a fuzzy model. Using the fuzzy model, we formulate the general control design problem in terms of LMIs and, subsequently, address particular synthesis issues. Firstly, we investigate the stabilization of the nonlinear plant in the presence of significant modeling error between the plant and its fuzzy model. Secondly, we treat the related problem of stabilization against parametric uncertainty in the nonlinear plant. Thirdly, we study the case in which conspicuous factors induce control in-

put constraints. Fourthly, whenever the state is not accessible, we solve the control implementation problem via estimated state feedback. The analysis will be presented in the continuous-time domain. Then, with minor modifications, it applies to the discrete-time case also.

2. Nonlinear Dynamics as the Convex Hull of Local Linear Models

We consider nonlinear systems described by

$$\dot{x} = A(x)x + B(x)u, \quad x \in \mathfrak{R}^n, \quad u \in \mathfrak{R}^m \quad (1)$$

where the matrix-valued functions $A \in \mathfrak{R}^{n \times n}$ and $B \in \mathfrak{R}^{n \times m}$ are continuously differentiable. The main result of the literature on fuzzy modeling states that inside an arbitrarily large compact subspace $\mathcal{X} \subset \mathfrak{R}^n$, the above class of nonlinear systems can be approximated by means of Fuzzy Basis Functions (FBFs) to desired accuracy [8, 13]. The fuzzy model that approximates the system matrix, A , for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$, stems from the following expansion in terms of FBFs [29]

$$A(x) = \sum_{i=1}^L \alpha_i(x)A_i + \Delta A(x), \quad \|\Delta A(x)\|_a \leq \bar{\mu} \quad (2)$$

where $\bar{\mu} > 0$ is arbitrarily small and L , which may depend on $\bar{\mu}$, is finite. The absolute matrix norm of $\Delta \in \mathfrak{R}^{n \times n}$ is $\|\Delta\|_a = n \max_{1 \leq k, l \leq n} |\delta_{kl}|$. The FBFs are defined as

$$\alpha_i(x) \triangleq \frac{w_i(x)}{\sum_{j=1}^L w_j(x)} \quad (3)$$

where $w_i : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a smooth bell-shaped function. Within the scope of this paper, the w_i 's will be identified with the Fuzzy Membership Functions (FMFs). Representative FMFs can be found in the literature, for example, see [8]. By definition, the FBFs are also bell-shaped;

$$\alpha_i(x) \geq 0; \quad \sum_{i=1}^L \alpha_i(x) = 1 \quad (4)$$

Now, using $B_s = [B \quad \mathbf{0}_{n \times (n-m)}]$,

$$B(x) = \sum_{i=1}^L \alpha_i(x)B_i + \Delta B(x), \quad \|\Delta B_s(x)\|_a \leq \bar{\mu} \quad (5)$$

Substitution from FBF expansions (2) and (5) into equation (1) yields

$$\dot{x} = \sum_{i=1}^L \alpha_i(x)(A_i x + B_i u) + \Delta A(x)x + \Delta B(x)u \quad (6)$$

for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$. The approximation $\sum_{i=1}^L \alpha_i(x)(A_i x + B_i u)$ constitutes a fuzzy model of the underlying system inside the compact subspace \mathcal{X} . Since \mathcal{X} can be

arbitrarily large, the restriction $x \in \mathcal{X}$ is rather weak and, in the sequel, will be omitted for brevity. Denoting the aggregative terms in the fuzzy model as below

$$\hat{A}(x) \triangleq \sum_{i=1}^L \alpha_i(x)A_i, \quad \hat{B}(x) \triangleq \sum_{i=1}^L \alpha_i(x)B_i \quad (7)$$

and using the FBF properties (4), it is readily seen that $\hat{A}(x) \in \text{Co}\{A_1, \dots, A_L\}$ and $\hat{B}(x) \in \text{Co}\{B_1, \dots, B_L\}$ where $\text{Co}\{\Delta_1, \dots, \Delta_L\}$ is the convex hull of the matrices $\Delta_1, \dots, \Delta_L$ [30]. This distinctive characteristic of the fuzzy model enables the LMI based formulation of several synthesis problems for nonlinear systems.

3. Nonlinear Control Design Based on Local Linear Models

The entire methodology developed in the sequel will be centered about equation (6), which comprises the fuzzy model and the modeling error terms. The latter can be expressed as a single perturbation term, f_U , given by

$$f_U(x, u) \triangleq \Delta A(x)x + \Delta B(x)u \quad (8)$$

From the uniform boundedness of $\|\Delta A\|_a$ and $\|\Delta B_s\|_a$, the perturbation satisfies the sector bounds

$$f_U^T(x, u)f_U(x, u) \leq \mu^2 \begin{bmatrix} x \\ u \end{bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} x \\ u \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

where $\mu = \bar{\mu}\sqrt{2}$. The above description is general enough to incorporate perturbations that originate from other sources, such as parametric uncertainty.

Herein, our main goal is to compute a static nonlinear controller

$$u = K(x)x, \quad K \in \mathfrak{R}^{m \times n} \quad (10)$$

that stabilizes the system (1). This is accomplished via stabilization of the fuzzy model \hat{A} and \hat{B} against the sector-bounded perturbation f_U . Furthermore, we extend the method to problems with control input constraints, such as $\|u\| \leq u_{\max}$, or inaccessible state variables. In the latter case, the system is sensed from its output $y = Cx$, where $y \in \mathfrak{R}^l$ and $C \in \mathfrak{R}^{l \times n}$. The static controller (10) is now replaced by the dynamic output feedback controller

$$u = K(z)z \quad (11)$$

$$\dot{z} = \hat{A}(z)z + \hat{B}(z)K(z)z + M(Cz - y) \quad (12)$$

where z is known as the estimated state and $M \in \mathfrak{R}^{n \times l}$ the observer gain. The differential equation that governs z is a state estimator or observer of the nonlinear system (1).

4. Static State Feedback Synthesis Using LMIs

The formulation of the control design problem in terms of LMIs is based on the closed loop of equation (6) with static feedback (10) given below

$$\dot{x} = (\hat{A}(x) + \hat{B}(x)K(x))x + f_U(x) \quad (13)$$

where $f_U(x)$, a simplified notation for $f_U(x, Kx)$, satisfies the sector bounds

$$f_U^T(x)f_U(x) \leq \mu^2 x^T \begin{bmatrix} I_n \\ K \end{bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} I_n \\ K \end{bmatrix} x \quad (14)$$

and combines both modeling error and parametric uncertainty. For an amount of perturbation measured by μ , the following lemma provides a sufficient condition so that the controller (10) renders system (6) and hence (1) asymptotically stable (a.s.)

Lemma 1 Suppose there exist $\bar{Q} > 0$, $\bar{Q} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $\bar{Y} = \bar{Y}(x) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, and $\tau > 0$ that satisfy the following inequality

$$\begin{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \bar{Q}\hat{A}^T + \hat{A}\bar{Q} \\ +\bar{B}\bar{Y} + \bar{Y}^T\bar{B}^T \\ +\tau^{-1}I_n \end{pmatrix} & \mu \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q} & \bar{Y}^T \end{bmatrix} \\ \mu \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q} \\ \bar{Y} \end{bmatrix} & -\tau^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} I_n & \\ & I_m \end{bmatrix} \end{bmatrix} < 0 \quad (15)$$

Then, the closed loop (13), subject to (14), with $K(x) = \bar{Y}(x)\bar{Q}^{-1}$ is a.s.

Observe that inequality (15) is linear in the variables \bar{Q} and $\bar{Y}(x)$. This implies that the stabilization problem can be solved by searching for matrices \bar{Q} and $\bar{Y}(x)$ that satisfy inequality (15). The general form of $\bar{Y}(x)$, however, prevents further exploitation of such linearity. In the sequel, we provide $\bar{Y}(x)$ with specific structure and hence facilitate the solution of the stabilization problem.

Linear Stabilizer

The simplest structure the control input, u , could possibly have is linear. In that case, the gain matrix K and hence \bar{Y} is independent of the state vector x .

Theorem 1 Suppose there exists $Q = Q^T > 0$ and Y such that

$$\begin{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} QA_i^T + A_iQ \\ +B_iY + Y^TB_i^T \\ +I_n \end{pmatrix} & \mu \begin{bmatrix} Q & Y^T \end{bmatrix} \\ \mu \begin{bmatrix} Q \\ Y \end{bmatrix} & - \begin{bmatrix} I_n & \\ & I_m \end{bmatrix} \end{bmatrix} < 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, L \quad (16)$$

Then, the closed loop (13), subject to (14), with linear gain $K = YQ^{-1}$ is a.s.

If the fuzzy approximate \hat{B} fits B exactly and parametric uncertainty is absent from the input matrix, inequality (9), which characterizes the perturbation term, becomes

$$f_U^T(x)f_U(x) \leq \mu^2 x^T x \quad (17)$$

In this case, the measure μ accounts for modeling error and parametric uncertainty in the system matrix, A . Furthermore, the sufficient condition (16) in the above theorem, assumes the simplified form

$$\begin{bmatrix} QA_i^T + A_iQ + B_iY + Y^TB_i^T + I_n & \mu Q \\ \mu Q & -I_n \end{bmatrix} < 0, \quad i = 1, \dots, L \quad (18)$$

Remark 1 We can determine the feasibility of inequalities (16) and hence (18) by solving for the unknown matrices Q and Y . Firstly, let us observe that the feasibility of inequalities (16) can be counted via minimization of the largest among the maximum eigenvalues of their LHS matrices. In doing so, the LMIs themselves along with the LMI $Q > 0$ are treated as constraints. The resulting optimization, known as the EigenValue Problem (EVP), is convex, since its constraints are jointly convex in the optimization variables Q and Y . Secondly, efficient interior point algorithms are available for solving such convex programs [25]. Several software packages, such as the LMI toolbox for use with MATLAB [31], have incorporated these algorithms into LMI solvers.

Nonlinear Stabilizer

We augment the structure of the controller as below

$$u = \sum_{j=1}^L \alpha_j(x)K_j x \quad (19)$$

where the gain matrices, K_j , are independent of the state vector x .

Theorem 2 Suppose there exist $Q = Q^T > 0$ and $\{Y_1, \dots, Y_L\}$ such that the following condition holds for $i = 1, \dots, L$ and $j = i, \dots, L$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} QA_i^T + A_iQ \\ +B_iY_j + Y_j^TB_i^T \\ +I_n \end{pmatrix} & \mu \begin{bmatrix} Q & Y_j^T \end{bmatrix} \\ \mu \begin{bmatrix} Q \\ Y_j \end{bmatrix} & - \begin{bmatrix} I_n & \\ & I_m \end{bmatrix} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} QA_j^T + A_jQ \\ +B_jY_i + Y_i^TB_j^T \\ +I_n \end{pmatrix} & \mu \begin{bmatrix} Q & Y_i^T \end{bmatrix} \\ \mu \begin{bmatrix} Q \\ Y_i \end{bmatrix} & - \begin{bmatrix} I_n & \\ & I_m \end{bmatrix} \end{bmatrix} < 0 \quad (20)$$

Then, the PDC (19) with the gains $K_j = Y_jQ^{-1}$ renders the closed loop (13) a.s. against uncertainty that is subject to (14).

Remark 2 The nonlinear stabilization is also tackled as an LMI problem in the variables Q and Y_j , $j = 1, \dots, L$. The related convex optimization is subject to $\frac{L(L+1)}{2}$ constraints compared with L in the linear case. The LMIs (20), however, form a weaker sufficient condition than their counterparts in (16). The latter require existence of a single stabilizing gain common for all subsystems.

Control Input Constraints

Consider the PDC (19) and the matrices Q and Y_j , $j = 1, \dots, L$, that satisfy the LMIs (20). It is known that $x^T(0)Q^{-1}x(0) \leq 1$ or, equivalently,

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & x^T(0) \\ x(0) & Q \end{bmatrix} \geq 0 \quad (21)$$

infers $x^T(t)Q^{-1}x(t) \leq 1$, for all $t \geq 0$, [25]. Let us denote this invariant ellipsoid by \mathcal{E} . Clearly,

$$\max_{t \geq 0} \|u(t)\| \leq \max_{1 \leq j \leq L} \sqrt{\lambda_{\max}(Q^{-\frac{1}{2}}Y_j^T Y_j Q^{-\frac{1}{2}})}$$

This suggests that inequality (21) and

$$\lambda_{\max}(Q^{-\frac{1}{2}}Y_j^T Y_j Q^{-\frac{1}{2}}) \leq u_{\max}^2, \quad j = 1, \dots, L$$

suffices for $\|u(t)\| \leq u_{\max}$, where u_{\max} limits the available control input. Thus, such control constraint can be incorporated into Theorem 2 by appending the hypothesis with the LMIs (21) and

$$\begin{bmatrix} Q & Y_j^T \\ Y_j & u_{\max}^2 \end{bmatrix} \geq 0, \quad j = 1, \dots, L \quad (22)$$

Moreover, we can extend the result to initial conditions lying in a ball $\|x(0)\| \leq \sigma$, where $\sigma \geq 0$. In this case, LMI (21) must be replaced by the LMI $Q \geq \sigma^2 I_n$.

5. Dynamic Output Feedback Synthesis using LMIs

As mentioned earlier, dynamic output feedback controllers are warranted whenever the state is not directly accessible for feedback. In this section, we compute the control law (11)–(12), which is based on the output, $y = Cx$, to stabilize the coupled equations of the closed-loop dynamics and the observer given below

$$\dot{x} = \hat{A}(x)x + BK(z)z + f_U(x) \quad (23)$$

$$\dot{z} = \hat{A}(z)z + BK(z)z + M(Cz - y) \quad (24)$$

To simplify presentation, we have assumed the input matrix, B , to be independent of x and known. Then, the sector bounds on the perturbation f_U are given by (17).

Subtracting equation (23) from (24), we get

$$\dot{z} - \dot{x} = \hat{A}(z)z - \hat{A}(x)x + MC(z - x) - f_U(x)$$

Furthermore,

$$\dot{z} - \dot{x} = \sum_{j=1}^L \beta_j(z-x)A_j(z-x) + MC(z-x) - f_U(x)$$

where $\beta_j(z-x) \geq 0$ and $\sum_{j=1}^L \beta_j(z-x) = 1$. Consider the nonlinear gain given by

$$K(z) = \sum_{i=1}^L \alpha_i(z)K_i$$

where the matrices K_i are constant. After manipulation, the closed-loop governing equation assumes the augmented form

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{z} \\ \dot{z} - \dot{x} \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{i=1}^L \sum_{j=1}^L \alpha_i(z)\beta_j(z-x)\tilde{A}_{ij} \begin{bmatrix} z \\ z-x \end{bmatrix} + \tilde{f}_U(x)$$

where

$$\tilde{A}_{ij} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} A_i + BK_i & MC \\ 0_{n \times n} & A_j + MC \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\tilde{f}_U(x) \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} 0_n \\ -f_U(x) \end{bmatrix}$$

We define the augmented state as $\tilde{x} \triangleq [z^T (z-x)^T]^T$ and the system matrix

$$\tilde{A}(\tilde{x}) \triangleq \sum_{i=1}^L \sum_{j=1}^L \alpha_i(\tilde{x})\beta_j(\tilde{x})\tilde{A}_{ij}$$

where the arguments of the α_i 's and β_j 's have been replaced by \tilde{x} . Thus, the closed loop is described by the augmented equation

$$\dot{\tilde{x}} = \tilde{A}(\tilde{x})\tilde{x} + \tilde{f}_U(x) \quad (25)$$

The linear growth bound of \tilde{f}_U is $\tilde{\mu} = \mu\sqrt{2}$.

Lemma 2 Suppose there exists $\tilde{P} > 0$, $\tilde{P} \in \mathfrak{R}^{2n \times 2n}$, such that

$$\tilde{A}^T(\tilde{x})\tilde{P} + \tilde{P}\tilde{A}(\tilde{x}) + \tilde{\mu}^2 I_{2n} + \tilde{P}^2 < 0$$

Then, the augmented equation (25), subject to uncertainty with linear growth bound, is a.s.

Now, the ensuing theorem formulates the dynamic output feedback stabilization as an LMI problem.

Theorem 3 Suppose

1. there exist $P > 0$, $P \in \mathfrak{R}^{n \times n}$, $S \in \mathfrak{R}^{n \times l}$ such that

$$\begin{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} A_j^T P + P A_j \\ + C^T S^T + S C \\ + \tilde{\mu}^2 I_n \\ P \end{pmatrix} & P \\ & -I_n \end{bmatrix} < 0, \quad j = 1, \dots, L \quad (26)$$

2. $Q > 0$, $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $Y_i \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ and, for $i, j = 1, \dots, L$,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \left(\begin{array}{c} QA_i^T + A_i Q \\ + BY_i + Y_i^T B^T + I_n \\ - MCR_j^{-1}(M, P)C^T M^T \\ \tilde{\mu}Q \end{array} \right) & \tilde{\mu}Q \\ & -I_n \end{bmatrix} < 0 \quad (27)$$

where $M = P^{-1}S$ and

$$R_j(M, P) \triangleq (A_j + MC)^T P + P(A_j + MC) + \tilde{\mu}^2 I_n + P^2 \quad (28)$$

Then, the closed loop (25), subject to uncertainty with linear growth bound, with $K_i = Y_i Q^{-1}$ is a.s.

The LMIs (26) and (27), associated with the observer and controller design respectively, must be solved in the order indicated in the hypothesis. The total number of LMIs needed to be solved is $L + L^2$. Clearly, the stabilizing feedback gains, K_i , are coupled with the observer gain, M , which has been solved for in LMI (26). By definition, the residual matrix R_j measures the stability degree of the observer associated with the local model A_j . In this context, LMI (27) synthesizes the gains K_i so that the poles of the closed-loop local model $A_i + BK_i$ have additional stability degree to account for the rate of convergence of the observer.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we developed a control synthesis framework for any nonlinear system that can be approximated by a fuzzy model. Within this framework, we formulated a fairly general stabilization problem as a convex program with LMI constraints. The resulting controller, linear or nonlinear, achieved its objective despite parametric uncertainty, estimated state feedback, and control input limitations. Usage of commercial LMI solvers, adds ease of computation to these virtues. Fuzzy model based control is primarily developed for nonlinear plants whose conventional modeling is impractical. The method, however, applies equally to nonlinear systems whose fuzzy model is derived from an existing conventional one and hence poses an alternative control design approach with the characteristics summarized above.

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